

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF DEMOGRAPHIC POLICY, POPULATION POLICY

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Annotation: This article describes the cases of population development, quantitative development of population, qualitative development of population, demographic policy, the main object of demographic policy, population reproduction, birth, death, marriage, divorce, cases.

Keywords: population policy, demographic policy, quantitative and qualitative development of the population, demographic education.

Demographic policy is a key part of population policy, which has different stages of development of society and specific features and directions in different countries. Population policy is more comprehensive than demographic policy and is a direction of socio-economic policy pursued for the purpose of population development.

Population development while their own in order to its also quantitative qualitative features changing in progress show will be . Of the population quantitative development deganda known period , known territory population of or in terms of the number of the nation changing borshi understood . Of the population qualitative development is , basically his health , average life vision , knowledge degree and known education take in perfection own expression finds . Population development socio-economic development organic part and he is his own into basically from family , family in the environment they are was . Delay industry slowly slow evolving go as a result mexnatga in preparation special knowledge , special activity necessary become remained . This is a necessity in the state

education system yanda in development , to young people naxsus knowledge giving , profession to teach need created . As a result in our country education system formed found and developed . Current period In Uzbekistan population policy basic purpose his qualitative development formed from consists of.

Of the population qualitative development the following own into takes _

- population health condition , children and mothers death average life period :
- of the population education degree and his composition : - population profession readiness level :
- of the population social composition and social mobility :
- of the population urbanization :
- of the population regional movement :
- of the population spiritual and cultural values and them save , respect .

In the Republic population policy reciprocal chambarchas connected joints formed found _ This joints demographic politics , population migration , urbanization and employment policies add possible . Demographic policy population policy organic part as its _ basic purpose population quantitative development stages consists of. Demographic policy basic objects of the population repeat barpo to be process is calculated .

Demographic policy through expected , desired population repeat barno type is achieved . As you know population repeat barpo to be birth , death , marriage , divorce such as demographic processes with directly depends on . So that 's it processes policy way with society by management is also demographic policy situations . Society development look if we throw , demographic processes , in particular birth , marriage society by managed witness we will Even this about eng ancient scientists Aflotun and Aratsu centuries . __ Old In Rome birth and nikohni ozod people in the middle supporting , laws __ acceptance made . Feudalism in society while by religion so solid laws created in them marriage , unlimited birth and big families population regularly multiply to go omili as protection made , supported

__ In Europe capitalist functional remove method development esa demographic processes new problems, directions come output cause was __ Industry development city life style expansion , women social functional in the output participation reach due to , in the family to the child which was Demand decreased . A lot children in women , capitalist functional remove conditions series economic problems to the body came , as a result birth spontaneously kamaya began . Capitalist functional remove method advanced France and other Europe countries birth of the XIX century first on anniversary from kamaya went . This to the twentieth century in the states come population of course growth finally decreased gone __

Population repeat barpo to be expanded standing shortened round passed __ As a result this countries population aging “ Demographic aging ” process happen was __ This is also the state by special demographic policy take to go demand did . In France in 1946 birth lift through population amount increase achieve in order to to families first and second especially third of their children at birth separately pension separated . He was born in 1960-1970 lift purpose demographic policy other advanced countries __ __ was given . But this states political property form birth multiply for all measure measures in use some problems quoting produces was

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